

Course of Cyclization in the Formation of Alicyclic Rings. Part III*

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Along lines previously followed by Chakravarti, it has been observed that Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate leads to ethyl 4-ethylcyclopentanone-2, 4-dicarboxylate and not ethyl 3-ethylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate. Similarly, ethyl 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate cyclizes to ethyl 4-n-propylcyclopentanone-2, 4-dicarboxylate and not ethyl 3-n-propylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate.

A reinvestigation of the Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate, by application of physical methods, indicates that in the cyclized product ethyl 4-methylcyclopentanone-2, 4-dicarboxylate may be present to the extent of 95 per cent, the remaining 5 per cent being ethyl 3-methylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate.

ONE of the most well studied cases of Dieckmann cyclization of a polycarboxylic ester, with more than one possibility for ring closure, is that of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (I). This reaction was first utilized by Ruzicka¹ in his synthesis of fenchone. He had his required ketoacid (IV) smoothly by hydrolysis of the Dieckmann cyclization product (II) and/or (III) and was not concerned with the structure of the cyclized product. Later, Baker² carried out a critical study of the course of cyclization in this particular case based on studies on the oxidative degradation of the cyclized ester, in view of the suitability of this ester in the synthesis of products related to the bile acids. He apparently established that the cyclization leads to ethyl 3-methylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate (II) and not ethyl 4-methylcyclopentanone-2, 4-dicarboxylate (III). Banerjee³, also interested in synthetic work in the field of bile acids and sex hormones, on the basis of the findings of Baker, utilised this cyclization in the synthesis of the bicyclic ketone (V). The cyclization was studied in a proper manner by Chakravarti⁴⁻⁸, by following a direct procedure in fixing up the point of cyclization with appropriate substituents and comparison of the product of hydrolysis with authentic specimens of the two alternative products corresponding to (II) and (III). It was thus unambiguously established that the particular cyclization leads to (III) and not (II), contrary to the findings of Baker, and that the bicyclic ketone synthesised by Banerjee was (VI) and not (V) (cf. Banerjee⁹).

Proceeding in a similar manner, in connection with studies on camphorquinone rearrangement, it was observed by Chakravarti¹⁰⁻¹³ that sodium cyclization of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1, 3, 5-tricarboxylate (VII) leads to the ketoester (VIII) and not (IX). It was also observed by Chakravarti¹⁴ that cyclization of ethyl $\beta\beta$ -dimethyladipate (X) with sodium gave the keto-ester (XI) and not (XII).

On the basis of the results obtained in the Dieckmann cyclizations of the above mentioned polycarboxylic esters as also those of a number of others, a number of useful conclusions were arrived at by Chakravarti¹⁴⁻¹⁷ as enumerated below :

- (i) The action of sodium on the ester of a β -alkyl -adipic or -pimelic acid, having two alternatives for cyclization, may be expected to lead to a ketonic ester in which the reactive methylene group, nearer to the alkyl radical remains unaffected by preference. The other isomer in such a case, if produced at all, can only be in much smaller amount.
- (ii) In the case of a β -carbethoxy-adipic or -pimelic ester, having two alternatives for cyclization, the product of sodium condensation usually leads to a mixture of the two isomeric keto-esters in which the keto-ester formed by interaction of the α -methylene group with the carbethoxy group at the other end of the chain predominates.

* For Part II, see reference No. 23.

(iii) In the case of the ester of a β -alkyl-adipic or -pimelic acid, in which the α -methylene group is the only methylene group present in the molecule adjacent to a carbethoxy group and suitable for the cyclization, the sodium condensation proceeds smoothly in spite of the deactivating influence of the alkyl group.

(iv) The deactivating influence of the alkyl group on the adjacent methylene group appears to be due to its strong electron releasing properties.

(v) In the case of an adipic or pimelic ester having both an alkyl group and a carboalkoxy group attached to the β -carbon atom, the effect of the alkyl group predominates, and the α -methylene group of the starting ester remains intact in the cyclized product by preference if there is the other possibility for the cyclization of the ester through the reactive methylene group near the other end of the chain.

(vi) As the effect of deactivation of a methylene group by an adjacent alkyl group is much more pronounced than the activating influence of a carboalkoxy group on the adjacent methylene group, it is inferred that quantitatively the positive or electron releasing character of an alkyl group is much greater than the negative or electron accepting character of a carboalkoxy group.

The failure in the attempted synthesis of 1-methyl-bicyclo-[4.3.0]-nonane-5, 9-dione by Goldberg, Hunziker, Billeter and Rosenberg¹⁸ through Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1, 2, 5-tricarboxylate could be smoothly explained on the basis of the postulations of Chakravarti¹⁹. It may be mentioned that Goldberg and his collaborators were interested in this reaction in connection with their work in the field of steroids and sex hormones. As in the cases of Baker and Banerjee, it was shown on the basis of the findings of Chakravarti that this type of cyclization is not suitable for the desired syntheses of steroidal moieties with the angular methyl group. The complicated and paradoxical case of cyclization of ethyl pentane-1, 2, 5-tricarboxylate, studied previously by Dobson, Ferns and Perkin²⁰, Chatterjee, Das and Barpujari²¹, and N. K. Chakravarty and Banerjee²², is also explicable on the basis of Chakravarti's²³ findings.

As the positive character in the series of alkyl groups increases in the following order :

it may be inferred that the effect of the latter groups would be parallel to or even more pronounced than that of methyl group. In this respect it is interesting to record here the results of an investigation on the deactivating influence of ethyl and n-propyl groups on adjacent reactive methylene groups in such cyclization reactions as in Chart I. Short communications covering these results appeared previously²⁴⁻³¹.

For the purpose of the present investigation, ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=Et) was prepared as in Chart III (R=Et) by condensing methyl homolaevulinate²⁵ (XXIII, R=Et)

Chart I

with ethyl cyanoacetate, addition of hydrogen cyanide to the unsaturated cyano-ester (XXIV, R=Et), hydrolysis of the dicyano-ester (XXV, R=Et) formed to the corresponding tricarboxylic acid (as XIII, R=Et) and subsequent esterification. Dieckmann cyclization of the tricarboxylic ester was carried out in the usual way and the cyclized sodio-salt was heated with methyl iodide. The methylated product was hydrolysed with dilute acid to obtain the methylated keto-acid, m.p. of semicarbazone 189°-190° (decomp.), and with strong alcoholic caustic potash to obtain the methylated tricarboxylic acid, m.p. 148°-149° (cf. Chart II, R=Et)²⁷. Both the possible isomers of the keto-acid and the tricarboxylic acid were prepared by unambiguous methods, as stated below (Chart IV and Chart V), for purposes of direct comparison. As a result the keto-acid obtained as above was found to be identical with 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Et) and the tricarboxylic acid identical with 2-ethylpen-

tane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et). This is in conformity with the generalisations arrived at as enumerated above.

The dicyano-ester (XXV, R=Et) was methylated with methyl iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide to (XXVI, R=Et) as in Chart IV. It was hydrolysed to 3-ethyl-n-pentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XX, R=Et), which could not be obtained in the crystalline state. The corresponding ester was cyclized with finely divided sodium when ethyl 3-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-3, 5-dicarboxylate (XXVII, R=Et)²⁶ was obtained. On hydrolysis with dilute acid it gave authentic specimen of 3-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=Et), m.p. of semicarbazone 210° (decomp.).

For preparation of the authentic samples of 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Et) and 2-ethyl-n-pentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et)²⁴, ethyl propionylacetate

Chart - III

R = Et, n-Pr

Chart - IV

R = Et, n-Pr

(XXVIII, R=Et) was condensed with ethyl α-bromopropionate in presence of sodium ethoxide to (XXIX, R=Et), which was hydrolysed and then esterified to the keto-ester (XXX, R=Et). The latter

was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate to the unsaturated cyano-ester (XXXI, R=Et) and then with hydrogen cyanide to the dicyano-ester (XXXII, R=Et) (as in Chart V). On hydrolysis 2-ethyl-

Chart V

n-pentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et), m.p. 148°-149° was obtained. The corresponding triethyl ester was cyclized with finely divided sodium to ethyl 3-ethyl-5-methylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate (XXXIII, R=Et), which on hydrolysis with dilute acid gave 4-ethyl-2-methyl cyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Et), m.p. of semicarbazone 189-190° (decomp.).

For the work in the *n*-propyl series, methyl β -butyrylpropionate (XXIII, R=*n*-Pr) was condensed (cf. Chart III) with ethyl cyanoacetate to the unsaturated cyano-ester (XXIV, R=*n*-Pr) which gave the dicyano-ester (XXV, R=*n*-Pr) with hydrogen cyanide. The latter on hydrolysis followed by esterification gave ethyl 2-*n*-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=*n*-Pr). As in the previous case (with ethyl

group) this triethyl ester was cyclized³¹ with finely divided sodium and then methylated *in situ* with methyl iodide. The methylated product was hydrolysed with dilute acid to obtain the methylated keto-acid, m.p. of semicarbazone 206°-207° (decomp.), and with strong alcoholic caustic potash to obtain the methylated tricarboxylic acid, m.p. 173-174° (cf. Chart II, R=*n*-Pr). Both the possible isomers of the keto-acid and the tricarboxylic acid were prepared by unambiguous methods as in the previous case (cf. Chart IV and Chart V) for purposes of direct comparison. As a result, the keto-acid obtained as above was found to be identical with 2-methyl-4-*n*-propylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=*n*-Pr) and the tricarboxylic acid identical with 2-*n*-propylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=*n*-Pr). Thus in this case also the results obtained

are in conformity with the generalisations arrived at earlier.

For preparation of the authentic samples of 2-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=n-Pr)³⁰ and 3-n-propyl-n-pentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XX, R=n-Pr) the dicyano-ester (XXV, R=n-Pr) was methylated with methyl iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide to (XXVI R=n-Pr) as in Chart IV. It was hydrolysed to the tricarboxylic acid (XX, R=n-Pr) which could not be obtained in the crystalline state. The corresponding ester was cyclized with finely divided sodium when ethyl 2-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3, 5-dicarboxylate (XXVII, R=n-Pr) was obtained. On hydrolysis with dilute acid it gave 2-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=n-Pr), m.p. of semicarbazone 229°-230° (decomp.).

Authentic specimens of the other isomers of the keto-acid (XXI, R=n-Pr) and the tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=n-Pr) were prepared²⁸ by condensing ethyl butyrylacetate (XXVIII, R=n-Pr) with ethyl α -bromopropionate in presence of sodium ethoxide to (XXIX, R=n-Pr). It was hydrolysed and then esterified to the keto-ester (XXX, R=n-Pr) which was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate to the unsaturated cyano-ester (XXXI, R=n-Pr) and subsequently converted into the dicyano-ester (XXXII, R=n-Pr) with addition of hydrogen cyanide. This on hydrolysis gave 2-n-propyl-n-pentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=n-Pr), m.p. 173-174°. The corresponding tricarboxylic ester was cyclized with finely divided sodium to 5-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate (XXXIII, R=n-Pr) which on hydrolysis with dilute acid afforded 2-methyl-4-n-propylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=n-Pr), m.p. of semicarbazone 206-207° (decomp.).

For having a more critical quantitative study of the position the cyclization of ethyl-2-methylbutane-1,

2, 4-tricarboxylate (I) was reinvestigated. For this purpose authentic specimens of methyl 2, 3-dimethylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylate (as XXII, R=Me) and methyl 2, 4-dimethylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylate (as XXI, R=Me) were prepared from the corresponding keto-acid which were obtained by the method of Chakravarti⁴. For convenience these two products are designated as Product A and Product B respectively. As was done previously, the cyclized product of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate was methylated *in situ* (cf. Chart II, R=Me) and then hydrolysed with dilute acid to the keto-acid. Though it was established previously that the product is really 2, 4-dimethylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Me) it may contain small amount of the other isomer, 2, 3-dimethylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=Me). In view of this possibility, the crude mixture of the keto-acids as obtained in this way was converted into corresponding methyl esters. It is designated as Product D.

The ir curves of Product A, Product B and Product D are as in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively. It may be noted that some of the peaks are present in all the three products, e.g. 775, 953, 1046, 1162, 1433, and 1729 cm^{-1} , while there are others which are common only to Product B and Product D, e.g. 733, 858, 913, 1110, 1133 and 1313 cm^{-1} . In some of the other cases product B and Product D have identical peaks whereas the corresponding peak of Product A is somewhat shifted in position. From a study of the ir spectra it is evident that Product D consists practically wholly of Product B. It is, however, extremely difficult to draw any conclusion as to the absence or presence of small amount of Product A in Product D.

Several laborious attempts were made for separation of the constituents of the mixture of isomers (Product D) by column chromatography but the results were not satisfactory.

Fig. 1. ir curve of product A.

Fig. 2. ir curve of product B.

Fig. 3. ir curve of product D.

A study of the glc curves of the three products is found to be much more useful and interesting. These are presented in figures 4, 5 and 6 respectively. It may be mentioned that Product A and Product B are each capable of existing in two stereoisomeric forms, Product A as (XXXIV) and (XXXV), and Product B as (XXXVI) and (XXXVII) (cf. Chart VI). The two peaks in figure 4 evidently represent the two stereoisomers of Product A. Similarly, the two peaks in figure 5 represent the two stereoisomers of Product B. It may be noted that the glc curve of Product D, as in figure 6, covers two major and one minor peaks. The peak A_1 of Product A (Fig. 4) is in a position close to that of B_2 of Product B (Fig. 5) and there is a chance of overlapping of these peaks in Fig. 6. On the other hand, peak A_2 of Product A (Fig. 4) and peak B_1 of Product B (Fig. 5) are in widely divergent positions and no question of overlapping of these peaks should arise in Fig. 6. The peak D_1 of Product D (Fig. 6) is in the same position

as the peak B_1 of Product B (Fig. 5) and the very small peak D_3 of Product D (Fig. 6) is in the same position as the peak A_2 of Product A (Fig. 4). The peak D_2 of Product D (Fig. 6) corresponds to the controversial nearly overlapping peaks A_1 (Fig. 4) and B_2 (Fig. 5). Thus the Product D consists for the most part of Product B and only very little (*ca.* 5 per cent) of Product A. During the conversion of the cyclized product, after methylation, into the methyl ester of the mixed keto-acids (Product D) there is some chance for loss of yield. Assuming this loss to be proportional in the cases of the two isomers, it appears that Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl-2-methylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (I) leads to about 95 per cent of ethyl 4-methylcyclopentanone-2, 4-dicarboxylate (III) and about 5 per cent of ethyl 3-methylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate (II). In view of the greater positive character of ethyl and *n*-propyl groups, as compared to methyl, the yield of the minor isomer is expected to be much less in the two other cyclizations presented in this paper ($R=Et, n-Pr$).

Fig. 4. glc curve of product A.

Fig. 6. glc curve of product D.

Fig. 5. glc curve of product B.

Chart VI

(XXXIV)

(XXXV)

(XXXVI)

(XXXVII)

Experimental*Preparation of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=Et) :*

A useful starting material for the synthesis of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate was found to be methyl homolaevulinate (XXIII, R=Et)²⁵. The method of Friedmann³² (Method I) involving condensation of ethyl propionylacetate³²⁻³⁴ with ethyl bromoacetate (cf. Fichter and Pfister³⁵) in presence of finely divided sodium in ether, followed by hydrolysis and esterification was found by us to give satisfactory yield. The yield of ethyl propionylsuccinate was somewhat improved by us²⁵ using ethyl chloroacetate in conjunction with dry sodium iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide. Another method was developed by us²⁵ involving condensation of β -carbomethoxypropionyl chloride with ethyl methylmalonate in presence of finely divided sodium in benzene, followed by hydrolysis and esterification (Method II). This was found to give good yield of methyl homolaevulinate. But the best method (Method III) found by us consists in condensation of β -carbomethoxypropionyl chloride with cadmium diethyl (cf. Gilman and Nelson³⁶, Cason³⁷).

Methyl homolaevulinate (Method II) :

Ethyl methylmalonate (34.8g) was added to finely divided sodium (4.6 g) in dry thiophene-free benzene (50 ml). The sodiosalt thus formed was cooled in ice, β -carbomethoxypropionyl chloride (36.5 g) added dropwise and the mixture kept overnight. It was then refluxed for 10 hr, treated with water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The oily layer was taken out, washed, dried and distilled. Methyl $\delta\delta$ -dicarbethoxy- γ -keto-caproate was distilled at 172°-174°/6 mm, yield 27 g. This tricarboxylic ester (25 g) was hydrolysed with 4 volumes of 10 per cent hydrochloric acid by heating on a sand bath for 8 hr. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness and extracted with benzene. After removal of benzene, homolaevulinic acid was obtained as an oily mass, yield 11 g. The crude acid (10 g) was taken in dry methanol (35 ml) and methanolic hydrogen chloride saturated at 0° (3.5 ml) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 25 hr, excess alcohol was removed and the residual portion taken in ether. It was washed, dried and solvent removed. On distillation, methyl homolaevulinate was obtained, b.p. 85°-86°/8 mm, yield 8.5 g.

Methyl homolaevulinate (Method III) :

Ethyl magnesium bromide was prepared in a three-necked flask (1 litre) fitted with a reflux condenser,

a dropping funnel and a mercury-sealed Hershberg stirrer of tantalum wire. A slow stream of dry nitrogen was passed through the flask and allowed to escape through the condenser and a U-tube with mercury seal. Magnesium turnings (18.1 g) covered with dry ether (110 ml) was allowed to react with a solution of ethyl bromide (82 g) in dry ether (265 ml). When the reaction was complete, the flask was cooled in an ice-bath and finely powdered, anhydrous cadmium chloride (73.5 g) was carefully added. The ice-bath was then removed, the mixture stirred for some time and the product heated under reflux for about an hour. Ether was rapidly distilled from the reaction vessel. Dry thiophene-free benzene (260 ml) was added at this point and the distillation was continued until an additional 125 ml of the distillate was collected. A second portion of dry benzene (260 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed with vigorous stirring for a few minutes. The heating bath was then removed and β -carbomethoxypropionyl chloride (5.6 g) in dry benzene (60 ml) was slowly added. The mixture was stirred under reflux for an additional one hour. The product was cooled in an ice-bath and decomposed with ice and 20 per cent sulphuric acid. The aqueous phase was separated, extracted with benzene and the combined benzene layer washed, dried, solvent removed and the residue distilled, b.p. 85°-86°/8 mm, yield 50 g.

1-Carbethoxy-4-carbomethoxy-1-cyano-2-ethyl- Δ^1 -butene (XXIV, R=Et) :

Methyl homolaevulinate (45 g) was condensed³⁸ with ethyl cyanoacetate (36 g) in presence of ammonium acetate (4.7 g), glacial acetic acid (7.2 g) and dry benzene (60 ml) by refluxing in an oil bath at 145-160° for 3-4 hr and using a water separator. The product was worked up by washing with water and removing the solvent by distillation. The unsaturated cyano-ester had b.p. 155°-160°/6-7 mm, yield 37 g. (Found : C, 60.6 ; H, 7.4 ; N, 5.4 per cent ; Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₇O₄N : C, 60.2 ; H, 7.2 ; N, 5.9 per cent).

1-Carbethoxy-4-carbomethoxy-1, 2-dicyano-2-ethylbutane (XXV, R=Et) :

The unsaturated cyano-ester (XXIV, R=Et) (35 g) dissolved in absolute alcohol (180 ml) was treated³⁹⁻⁴¹ with potassium cyanide (19.5 g) in water (105 ml), and then dropwise with hydrochloric acid (40 ml, 20 per cent) with cooling in ice. After one hour, it was diluted with a large volume of water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The oil separated was taken up in ether, washed with water

and solvent removed, b.p. 190°-91°/6-7 mm, yield 33.5 g. (Found : C, 58.3 ; H, 6.6 ; N, 10.9 per cent ; Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{18}O_4N_2$: C, 58.6 ; H, 6.8 ; N, 10.5 per cent).

Ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=Et) :

The above dicyanoester (34 g) was hydrolysed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid (160 ml) for 20 hr. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the residue taken up in ether. On evaporation of the solvent, crude acid (27 g) was obtained. It was esterified by refluxing for 40 hr with absolute alcohol (160 ml), benzene (50 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (8 ml), and using a water separator. After removal of excess alcohol, the residue was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. It was then washed, dried and solvent removed, b.p. 160°-65°/6-7 mm, yield 24 g. (Found : C, 59.2 ; H, 8.9 per cent ; Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{26}O_6$: C, 59.6 ; H, 8.7 per cent).

Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate and in situ methylation :

The tricarboxylic ester (10 g) was heated on a water bath with a fine suspension of sodium (0.92 g) in dry, thiophene-free benzene (25 ml) for an hour. It was cooled in ice, methyl iodide (5 ml) was added, kept overnight at room temperature and refluxed for 16 hr with the addition of a little methyl iodide from time to time. The product was then treated with ice-water, the benzene layer separated and the aqueous portion once extracted with a little benzene. The combined benzene layer was washed with water, solvent removed and distilled. The methylated keto dicarboxylic ester was distilled, b.p. 150°-51°/8-9 mm, yield 7.8 g. It gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 62.7 ; H, 8.3 per cent ; Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{25}O_5$; C, 62.2 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

Acid hydrolysis of the above methylated keto-dicarboxylic-ester : Formation of 2-ethylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et) :

The above product (3.5 g) was heated on the water-bath for 10 hr with potassium hydroxide (3.5 g) in 25 per cent aqueous alcoholic solution. The solvent was evaporated, acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The acid obtained on evaporation of the solvent was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid. It melted at 148-149°. There was no depression in melting point when it was mixed with an authentic specimen of 2-ethylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et)

synthesised for the purpose by an unambiguous method as described later.

(Found : C, 52.0 ; H, 6.8 per cent.

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_6$: C, 51.7 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

Ketonic hydrolysis of the above methylated keto-dicarboxylic-ester : formation of 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Et) :

The above methylated keto-dicarboxylic-ester (3.5 g) was heated on a sand bath for 25 hr with 5 volumes of 20 per cent hydrochloric acid. The clear solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate, extracted once with a little ether to remove any neutral matter, acidified, saturated with common salt and then extracted with ether. The keto-acid was obtained as a gummy viscous liquid. The semicarbazone after several crystallisations from aqueous alcohol melted at 189°-90° (decomp.). There was no depression in melting point on mixing it with an authentic semicarbazone of 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid synthesised for the purpose by an unambiguous method as described later.

(Found : C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.4 per cent.

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$: C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

Esterification of the above keto-acid to methyl 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylate :

The keto-acid (0.8 g) obtained above was esterified with absolute methanol (12 ml) and methanolic hydrochloric acid (1.2 ml) by gentle refluxing on the water bath for 10 hr. On treatment in the usual manner, a colourless liquid was obtained, b.p. 107°-108°/7-8 mm, yield 0.6 g.

(Found : C, 65.5 ; H, 8.6 per cent.

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{18}O_3$: C, 65.2 ; H, 8.8 per cent).

Synthesis of 3-ethyl-n-pentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XX, R=Et) and 3-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=Et) :

1-Carbomethoxy-4-carbomethoxy-3-ethyl-3, 4-dicyano-n-pentane (XXVI, R=Et) :

The dicyano-ester, 1-carbomethoxy-4-carbomethoxy-1, 2-dicyano-2-ethylbutane (XXV, R=Et) (18.5 g) was added to an ice-cold solution of sodium (1.62 g) in absolute alcohol (27 ml). Methyl iodide (5 ml) was then added to it, kept overnight and refluxed on the water bath for 15 hr with the addition of a little methyl iodide from time to time. It was then diluted with water, and the oil separated taken up in ether. The extract was washed with dilute potassium hydroxide solution and water, and then dried and solvent

removed. On distillation, a colourless mobile liquid was obtained, b.p. 186° - 187° / $6-7$ mm, yield 15.2 g. (Found : C, 60.5 ; H, 7.0 ; N, 9.6 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{20}O_4N_2$: C, 60.0 ; H, 7.2 ; N, 10.0 per cent).

Ethyl 3-ethyl-n-pentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylate (as XX, R=Et) :

The above ester (14.5 g) was hydrolysed with 5 volumes of concentrated hydrochloric acid by heating on a sand-bath for 20 hr. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue repeatedly extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent 3-ethyl-n-pentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XX, R=Et) (11 g) was obtained. It was then refluxed for 50 hr with absolute alcohol (120 ml), benzene (60 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (6.0 ml). Excess alcohol was removed, the residue cooled, treated with ice-water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed, dried and the solvent was removed. On distillation, the tricarboxylic ester was obtained, b.p. 160° - 165° / 7 mm, yield 8.5 g. (Found : C, 60.3 ; H, 9.1 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{28}O_6$: C, 60.7 ; H, 8.9 per cent).

For the preparation of pure 3-ethyl-n-pentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylic acid, the above ester (1.5 g) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml) by heating on a sand-bath for 8 hr. On usual treatment, a gummy product was obtained. It was not possible to obtain this acid in the crystalline state.

Ethyl 3-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-3, 5-dicarboxylate (XXVII, R=Et) :

The above tricarboxylic ester (5.3 g) was heated on a water bath with finely divided sodium (0.5 g) in dry, thiophene-free benzene (25 ml). The reaction was complete in 45 min. It was treated with ice-water, acidified with cold, dilute hydrochloric acid (5 per cent) and the benzene layer separated. After washing with water, the solvent was removed and the residual oil distilled, b.p. 162° - 163° / 10 mm, yield 3.2 g. The product gave intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 62.5 ; H, 8.4 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$: C, 62.2 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

Ketonic hydrolysis of the above product : Formation of 3-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=Et)

The above keto-dicarboxylic ester (2 g) was hydrolysed by heating for 20 hr with 20 per cent hydro-

chloric acid (25 ml). It was then neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter. The aqueous solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. The crude keto-acid was obtained as a viscous liquid on evaporation of the solvent. The semicarbazone was recrystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and chloroform as a fine microcrystalline powder, m.p. 210° (decomp.) A mixture of this semicarbazone with an equal amount of the semicarbazone of the keto-acid obtained by ketonic hydrolysis of the cyclized and methylated product of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate has m.p. 180° - 189° (decomp.) The depression in the mixed m.p. indicates that the two are different. (Found : C, 53.0 ; H, 7.6 ; N, 18.4 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$: C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

Methyl 3-ethyl-2-methyl cyclopentanone-3-carboxylate :

The keto-acid (0.7 g) was gently refluxed for 10 hr with absolute methanol (12 ml) and methanolic hydrogen chloride (1.2 ml). On treatment in the usual manner, the methyl ester was obtained, b.p. 95° / 6 mm, yield 0.45 g. (Found : C, 65.5 ; H, 8.5 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$: C, 65.2 ; H, 8.8 per cent).

Synthesis of 2-ethylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et) and of 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Et) :

Ethyl α -methyl- α' -propionyl succinate (XXIX, R=Et) :

Ethyl propionylacetate (XXVIII, R=Et) (45.2 g) was added dropwise to a solution of sodium (7.3 g) in absolute alcohol (125 ml). It was treated with ethyl α -bromopropionate (56.8 g), kept overnight and refluxed for 10 hr. The resulting product was diluted with water, extracted with ether, dried and the solvent evaporated. On distillation the ester boiling at 130° - 135° / 8 mm was obtained, yield 38 g.

Ethyl α -methyl- β -propionylpropionate (XXX, R=Et) :

The above product (65 g) was heated on a sand-bath for 12 hr with 5 volumes of hydrochloric acid (10 per cent). The clear solution was evaporated to dryness, extracted with ether and dry acid (30.5 g) thus obtained was refluxed for 25 hr with absolute alcohol (150 ml) and alcoholic hydrochloric acid (15 ml). After removal of the excess alcohol, the residue was taken in ether, washed, dried and solvent removed. The residue was distilled at 98° - 100° / 10 mm, yield 26.8 g.

Ethyl 1-cyano-2-ethyl- Δ^1 -pentene-1, 4-dicarboxylate (XXXI, R=Et) :

Ethyl α -methyl- β -propionylpropionate (26.8 g) was refluxed at 145°-55° for 4 hr with ethyl cyanoacetate (17.7 g) in presence of ammonium acetate (1.15 g), glacial acetic acid (1.8 g) and dry benzene (15 ml) and using a water separator. The product was then cooled, washed, the solvent removed and the residual oil distilled, b.p. 170°/10 mm, yield 18.9 g.

(Found : C, 62.5 ; H, 7.8 ; N, 5.6 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{21}O_4N$: C, 62.9 ; H, 7.9 ; N, 5.2 per cent).

Ethyl 1, 2-dicyano-2-ethylpentane-1, 4-dicarboxylate (XXXII, R=Et) :

The above unsaturated cyano-ester (18.9 g) was taken in spirit (90 ml) and a solution of potassium cyanide (9.3 g) in water (48 ml) added with shaking. The warm product was cooled in ice-water, treated dropwise with dilute 20 per cent hydrochloric acid (16 ml) and the mixture kept for 45 min at the room temperature. It was then diluted with a large volume of water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The heavy oil separating was extracted with ether, washed, dried and solvent removed. The residue afforded the dicyano ester, b.p. 197°-98°/9 mm, yield 17.8 g.

(Found : C, 61.5 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 9.9 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{22}O_4N_2$: C, 61.2 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 9.5 per cent).

Ethyl 2-ethylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (as XIX, R=Et) :

The dicyano-ester (16.8 g) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 ml) for 15 hr on a sand-bath. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness, extracted with ether, and the gummy residue obtained on removal of the solvent was dried, yield 14.0 g. This acid was refluxed with absolute alcohol (150 ml), concentrated sulphuric acid (7.3 ml) and dry benzene (75 ml) for 40 hr using a water separator. Excess alcohol was distilled and the residue extracted with ether. It was then washed, dried and the solvent removed. The ester (XIX, R=Et) was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 175°-76°/12 mm, yield 12.5 g. (Found : C, 61.1 ; H, 8.7 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{28}O_6$: C, 60.7 ; H, 8.9 per cent).

2-Ethylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=Et) :

The tricarboxylic ester (2 g) obtained above was hydrolysed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric

acid (20 ml) for 10 hr. The acid obtained as a highly viscous product was purified by several crystallisations from hot concentrated hydrochloric acid and finally from ethyl acetate. It melted at 148°-49°. It was found to be identical with the tricarboxylic acid obtained by acid hydrolysis of the methylated cyclized product of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid by comparison of mixed m.p. (Found : C, 52.0 ; H, 6.6 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_6$: C, 51.7 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-ethylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (as XIX, R=Et) :

The above tricarboxylic ester (5.3 g) taken in dry thiophene-free benzene (25 ml) was heated with pulverised sodium (0.5 g) on a water-bath. The reaction was complete in 45 min. The product was cooled, treated with ice-water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was washed, dried and on removal of the solvent ethyl 3-ethyl-5-methylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate (XXXIII, R=Et) was obtained, b.p. 150°-155°/12 mm, yield 3.2 g. It gave a deep violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

(Found : C, 62.6 ; H, 8.0 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$: C, 62.2 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=Et) :

The above keto-dicarboxylic ester (XXXIII, R=Et) (2.1 g) was heated with 20 per cent hydrochloric acid (25 ml) for 10 hr. The clear solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate, extracted once with ether and the aqueous solution then acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. The acid (1.5 g) obtained was directly converted to a semicarbazone, m.p. 189°-190° (decomp.). It was found to be identical with the semicarbazone of the keto-acid obtained by ketonic hydrolysis of the cyclized and methylated product of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate by comparison of mixed m.p.

(Found : C, 52.8 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 16.6 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$: C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

Methyl 4-ethyl-2-methylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylate (as XXI, R=Et)

The keto-acid (1.1 g) was esterified with absolute methanol (10 ml) and alcoholic hydrochloric acid

(1 ml) by heating on a water bath for 10 hr. The excess alcohol was removed, the residue taken in ether, washed, dried and distilled. The methyl ester having characteristic fruity odour boiled at 107-108°/7-8 mm, yield 0.8 g.

(Found : C, 65.6 ; H, 8.6 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$: C, 65.2 ; H, 8.8 per cent.)

Dieckmann Cyclization of ethyl 2-ethylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=Et) :

The ester (5.0 g) in dry benzene was heated on a water bath with pulverised sodium. The reaction was complete in 45 min. It was cooled, treated with ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was washed, dried and distilled, b.p. 162°-63°/10 mm, yield 2.9 g. It gave a deep violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

(Found : C, 61.3 ; H, 7.6 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$: C, 60.9 ; H, 7.9 per cent.)

3-Ethylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XVI, R=Et) :

The keto-ester (1.5 g) was hydrolysed with 10 per cent hydrochloric acid (25 ml) by heating for 12 hr. The solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate, extracted once with ether and the aqueous solution acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent, the keto-acid was obtained as a viscous mass. It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 164°.

(Found : C, 50.8 ; H, 7.0 ; N, 20.2 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_9H_{15}O_3N_3$: C, 50.7 ; H, 7.1 ; N, 19.7 per cent.)

Preparation of ethyl 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=n-Pr) :

Methyl β -butyrylpropionate (XXIII, R=n-Pr) :

n-Propylmagnesium bromide (magnesium 24.3 g ; n-propyl bromide 123 g) in ether was treated with finely powdered anhydrous cadmium chloride (98 g). Ether was then removed, and di-n-propyl cadmium thus formed was condensed with β -carbomethoxypropionyl chloride (120 g) in dry thiophene free benzene. The reaction was carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting complex on decomposition with dilute sulphuric acid afforded the methyl ester, b.p. 85°-86°/7 mm, yield 85 g.

1-Carbethoxy-4-carbomethoxy-1-cyano-2-n-propyl- Δ^1 -butene (XXIV, R=n-Pr) :

The above ester (35 g) was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate (25.5 g) in presence of ammonium

acetate (1.68 g), glacial acetic acid (2.6 g) and benzene (22 ml). The product gave on distillation the unsaturated cyano-ester, b.p. 160°-165°/7 mm, yield 20 g. (Found : C, 62.0 ; H, 7.4 ; N, 5.3 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{19}O_4N$: C, 61.6 ; H, 7.6 ; N, 5.5 per cent.)

1-Carbethoxy-4-carbomethoxy-1, 2-dicyano-2-n-propylbutane (XXV, R=n-Pr) :

The above cyano-ester (18.5 g) dissolved in spirit (90 ml) was treated with potassium cyanide (9.7 g) in water (50 ml), and then with a cold solution of concentrated hydrochloric acid (11.6 ml) and water (6.5 ml). After acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, the dicyano-ester was obtained, b.p. 190°-95°/7 mm, yield 18.7 g.

(Found : C, 60.4 ; H, 7.2 ; N, 9.7 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{20}O_4N_2$: C, 60.0 ; H, 7.2 ; N, 10.0 per cent.)

Ethyl 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=n-Pr) :

The dicyano-ester (18 g) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid, and the crude gummy product (15 g) thus obtained esterified with absolute alcohol (150 ml), dry benzene (50 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (7 ml) by refluxing for 40 hr. The ester was distilled at 175°-176°/7 mm, yield 12.5 g.

(Found : C, 60.3 ; H, 8.7 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{28}O_6$: C, 60.7 ; H, 8.9 per cent.)

Pure 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the above tricarboxylic ester (1.5 g) with concentrated hydrochloric acid. It was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid. On recrystallisation from ethyl acetate, the pure acid was obtained, m.p. 110°-112°.

(Found : C, 52.0 ; H, 6.8 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_6$: C, 51.7 ; H, 6.9 per cent.)

Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=n-Pr) and methylation in situ of the sodio-salt :

The tricarboxylic ester (9.5 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) was cyclized with finely divided sodium (0.82 g) and then methylated *in situ* with excess of methyl iodide. The resulting product was distilled at 145°-146°/5 mm, yield 5.3 g.

(Found : C, 63.8 ; H, 8.3 per cent.)

Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{24}O_5$: C, 63.4 ; H, 8.5 per cent.)

Acid hydrolysis of the methylated Keto-dicarboxylic ester : Formation of 2-n-propylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=n-Pr) :

The product obtained above was hydrolysed with caustic potash (2 g) in 25 per cent aqueous alcoholic solution. The acid obtained as a gummy residue was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 173°-174°. It was identical with 2-n-propylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid as there was no depression in melting point when mixed with an authentic specimen of the tricarboxylic acid synthesised by an unambiguous method as described later. (Found : C, 54.0 ; H, 7.5 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{18}O_6$; C, 53.7 ; H, 7.4 per cent).

Ketonic hydrolysis of the methylated keto-ester : Formation of 2-methyl-4-n-propylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=n-Pr) :

The methylated keto-dicarboxylate (2.3 g) described above was hydrolysed with 20 per cent hydrochloric acid. The semicarbazone of the keto-acid melted at 206°-207° (decomp.) It was identical with the semicarbazone of 2-methyl 4-n-propylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid as there was no depression in melting point when admixed with an authentic specimen of the semicarbazone of the keto-acid synthesised by an unambiguous method as described later. (Found : C, 55.3 ; H, 7.9 ; N, 18.0 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$: C, 54.8 ; H, 7.9 ; N, 17.4 per cent).

Synthesis of authentic specimens of 3-n-propylpentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XX, R=n-Pr) and of 2-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=n-Pr) :

The dicyano-ester (XXV, R=n-Pr) (18.7 g) as described earlier was methylated with excess methyl iodide in presence of sodium (1.53 g) in absolute alcohol (25 ml). On distillation, it gave an oily liquid, b.p. 185°-190°/6 mm, yield 16.5 g. (Found : C, 61.6 ; H, 7.3 ; N, 10.0 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{22}O_4N_2$: C, 61.2 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 9.5 per cent).

Ethyl 3-n-propylpentane-1, 3, 4-tricarboxylate (as XX, R=n-Pr) :

The above ester (15 g) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the crude acid (12 g) thus obtained was esterified with absolute alcohol

(120 ml) in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid (6 ml). The tricarboxylic ester boiled at 170°-175°/6 mm, yield 8.5 g. (Found : C, 62.2 ; H, 9.3 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{30}O_6$; C, 61.8 ; H, 9.2 per cent).

Ethyl 2-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3, 5-dicarboxylate (XXVII, R=n-Pr) :

The above tricarbonylic ester (5 g) was cyclized with sodium (0.45 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) in presence of a trace of absolute alcohol. The keto-ester was distilled at 170°-171°/8 mm, yield 2.9 g. It gave intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 63.7 ; H, 8.4 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{24}O_5$: C, 63.4 ; H, 8.5 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XXII, R=n-Pr)

The keto-diester (1.8 g) was hydrolysed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The semicarbazone of the keto-acid had m.p. 229°-230° (decomp.). A mixture of this semicarbazone with an equal amount of the semicarbazone of the keto-acid obtained by ketonic hydrolysis of the cyclized and methylated product of ethyl 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=n-Pr) had m.p. 200°-210° (decomp.). The depression in the mixed m.p. indicated that the two were different. (Found : C, 55.3 ; H, 8.1 ; N, 17.0 per cent. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$: C, 54.8 ; H, 7.9 ; N, 17.4 per cent).

Synthesis of authentic specimens of 2-n-propylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=n-Pr) and of 2-methyl-4-n-propylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=n-Pr).

Ethyl butyryl acetate (XXVIII, R=n-Pr) :

n-Propylmagnesium iodide (magnesium, 24.1 g, n-propyl iodide, 190 g) was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate (47 g). The ethyl ester was collected at 72°-73°/5 mm, yield 40 g.

Ethyl α -butyryl- α' -methylsuccinate (XXIX, R=n-Pr) :

It was obtained by condensation of ethyl butyryl acetate (21 g) with ethyl α -bromopropionate in presence of sodium (3.1 g) in absolute alcohol (51 ml). The product gave a colourless liquid, b.p. 130°-135°/7 mm, yield 27 g.

Ethyl β -butyryl- α -methylpropionate (XXX, R=n-Pr):

The acid (13.5 g) obtained by hydrolysis of the above ester was esterified to an oily liquid, b.p. 90°-92°/7 mm. yield 13 g.

Ethyl 1-cyano-2-n-propyl- Δ^1 -pentene-1, -4dicarboxylate (XXXI, R=n-Pr) :

The ester (26.5 g) obtained above was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate (16.2 g) in presence of ammonium acetate (1.32 g), glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and benzene (16 ml). The unsaturated cyano-ester was obtained as an oily liquid, b.p. 175°-180°/10 mm, yield 17.2 g.

(Found : C, 64.4 ; H, 8.1 ; N, 5.5 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{23}O_4N$: C, 64.0 ; H, 8.2 ; N, 5.0 per cent).

Ethyl 1, 2-dicyano-2-n-propylpentane-1, 4-dicarboxylate (XXXII, R=n-Pr) :

The above unsaturated cyano-ester (16.0 g) was treated with potassium cyanide (8.1 g) in presence of cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The dicyano-ester had b.p. 185°-188°/7 mm, yield 16 g.
(Found : C, 62.7 ; H, 7.7 ; N, 9.4 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{24}O_4N_7$: C, 62.3 ; H, 7.9 ; N, 9.1 per cent).

Ethyl 2-n-propylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (as XIX, R=n-Pr) :

The dicyano-ester (15 g) obtained as above was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The crude acid (11.5 g) was then esterified. The tricarboxylic ester, b.p. 180°-182°/8 mm, was obtained as a colourless liquid, yield 9.5 g.
Found : C, 62.2 ; H, 9.4 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{30}O_6$: C, 61.8 ; H, 9.2 per cent).

2-n-propylpentane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylic acid (XIX, R=n-Pr) :

The above ester (2 g) gave a gummy acid on hydrolysis. It was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 173°-174°. It was identical with the tricarboxylic acid obtained by acid hydrolysis of the methylated cyclized product of ethyl-2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate as there was no depression in melting point when they were mixed together.
(Found : C, 54.0 ; H, 7.3 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{18}O_6$: C, 53.7 ; H, 7.4 per cent).

Ethyl 5-methyl-3-n-propylcyclopentanone-2, 3-dicarboxylate (XXXIII, R=n-Pr) :

The triethyl ester (6 g) obtained as above was cyclized with pulverised sodium (0.55 g). The cyclic keto-diester was collected as a colourless liquid, b.p. 175°-176°/8-9 mm, yield 3.2 g. It gave intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.
(Found : C, 63.9 ; H, 8.8 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{24}O_5$: C, 63.4 ; H, 8.5 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-n-propylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid (XXI, R=n-Pr) :

The above keto-diester (2.5 g) was hydrolysed by dilute hydrochloric acid to the keto-acid, semicarbazone of which melted at 206°-207° (decomp). It was identical with the semicarbazone of the keto-acid obtained by ketonic hydrolysis of the methylated cyclized product of ethyl 2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate as there was no depression in melting point when they were mixed together.
(Found : C, 55.0 ; H, 8.1 ; N, 17.1 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$: C, 54.8 ; H, 7.9 ; N, 17.4 per cent).

Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl-2-n-propylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (XIII, R=n-Pr) :

The tricarboxylic ester (3.8 g) was cyclized with finely divided sodium (0.33 g) in dry benzene (15 ml) in presence of a trace of absolute alcohol. A colourless, sweet smelling liquid was obtained on distillation, b.p. 150°-151°/6 mm, yield 2.0 g. It gave intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.
(Found : C, 62.6 ; H, 8.4 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$: C, 62.2 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

3-n-propylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (XVI, R=n-Pr) :

The keto-dicarboxylic ester (1.2 g) obtained as above was hydrolysed by heating with 20 per cent hydrochloric acid (15 ml) for 20 hr. The keto-acid thus obtained was converted to a semicarbazone. It was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 194°-195° (decomp).
(Found : C, 52.6 ; H, 7.8 ; N, 19.1 per cent.
Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$: C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

Products A, B and D :

The keto-acids corresponding to Products A, B and D were previously prepared by Chakravarti

in the earliest paper⁴ amongst his publications in this series. In the present instance, in view of the requirement, these were prepared following the general outline of the procedure adopted by him earlier. However, in a number of steps in the present instance newer preparative methods, as in the cases of preparation in the 'ethyl series' and in the 'propyl series', were adopted. Details of these are not being presented here for brevity.

Synthesis of methyl 2, 3-dimethylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylate (XXXIV and XXXV in Chart VI; also as XXII, R=Me in Chart II) (Product A) :

The keto-acid (XXII, R=Me) (7 g) was refluxed with methanol (70 ml) and methanolic hydrogen chloride (5 ml) for 12 hr. Excess alcohol was removed and the residue diluted with ice-water. The separated oil was extracted with ether, washed and dried. The methyl ester was obtained as a sweet smelling colourless liquid, b.p. 95°-96°/7 mm, yield 5.5 g. (Found : C, 63.9 ; H, 8.1 per cent. Calcd. for C₉H₁₄O₃ : C, 63.5 ; H, 8.3 per cent).

The keto-ester was then converted to a semicarbazone, m.p. 212-213° (decomp.). An equal amount of this semicarbazone with that of Product D melted at 165-175° (decomp.). This indicates that they are different. (Found : C, 52.5 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 19.0 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇O₃N₃ : C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

Synthesis of methyl 2, 4-dimethylcyclopentanone-4-carboxylate (XXXVI and XXXVII in Chart VI; also as XXI, R=Me in Chart V) (Product B) :

The keto-acid (XXI, R=Me) (2.5 g) was refluxed with methanol (30 ml) in presence of methanolic hydrogen chloride (3 ml) for 10 hr. After the removal of excess alcohol, the residue was diluted with ice-water. The separated oil was extracted with ether, washed and dried. The methyl ester was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 95°-96°/7 mm, yield 1.9 g. (Found : C, 63.4 ; H, 8.2 per cent. Calcd. for C₉H₁₄O₃ : C, 63.5 ; H, 8.3 per cent).

It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 185° (decomp.). (Found : C, 52.6 ; H, 7.3 ; N, 19.1 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇O₃N₃ : C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

Preparation of Product D :

The keto-acid (XXI and/or XXII) (8 g) obtained by ketonic hydrolysis of the cyclized and methylated

product of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1, 2, 4-tricarboxylate (I) was refluxed with methanol (80 ml) and methanolic hydrogen chloride (8 ml) for 10 hr. Excess alcohol was removed, the residue treated with ice-water and extracted with ether. It was then washed, dried and the solvent removed. On distillation, Product D was obtained, b.p. 95°-96°/7 mm, yield 6.4 g. (Found : C, 63.0 ; H, 8.1 per cent. Calcd. for C₉H₁₄O₃ : C, 63.5 ; H, 8.3 per cent).

It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 185°-186° (decomp.). It was found to be identical with the semicarbazone of Product B as it showed no depression in melting point when they were mixed together. (Found : C, 52.4 ; H, 7.3 ; N, 19.2 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇O₃N₃ : C, 52.9 ; H, 7.5 ; N, 18.5 per cent).

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References

1. L. RUZICKA, *Ber.* 1917, **50**, 1362.
2. J. W. BAKFR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548.
3. D. K. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 423.
4. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 173.
5. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 189.
6. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 243.
7. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 247.
8. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 399.
9. D. K. BANERJEE, *Science & Culture*, 1944, **9**, 456.
10. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 301.
11. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *Current Science*, 1944, **13**, 158.
12. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 319.
13. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 322.
14. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1028.
15. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *Proc. National Inst. Sci. India*, 1960, **26A (Suppl. I)**, 48.
16. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. & Proc. Inst Chemists (India)*, 1961, **33**, 261.
17. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1025.
18. M. W. GOLDBERG, F. HUNZIKER, J. R. BILLETTER and H. R. ROSENBERG, *Helv. chim. Acta*, 1947, **30**, 200.
19. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *Experientia*, 1947, **3**, 149.
20. M. E. DOBSON, J. FERNS and W. H. PERKIN Jr., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 2010.
21. N. N. CHATTERJEE, B. K. DAS and G. N. BARPUJARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 161.
22. N. K. CHAKRAVARTY and D. K. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **23**, 377.

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23. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1315.
24. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 22.
25. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 62.
26. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 113.
27. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 165.
28. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1966, 14, 15.
29. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1966, 14, 127.
30. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1967, 15, 61.
31. R. N. CHAKRAVARTI and N. DUTTA, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1967, 15, 99.
32. E. FRIEDMANN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1936, 146, 159.
33. E. BLAISE, *Compt. Rend.*, 1901, 132, 978.
34. R. WILLSTATTER and C. H. CLARKE, *Ber*, 1914, 47, 298.
35. F. FICHTER and A. PEISTER, *Ber*, 1904, 37, 1997.
36. H. GILMAN and J. F. NELSON, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1936, 55, 518.
37. J. CASON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1106.
38. A. C. COPE, C. M. HOFMANN, C. WYCKOFF and E. HARDENBERGH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452.
39. E. HOPE and W. SHELDON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 2223.
40. A. LAPWORTH and J. A. MCRAE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 2752.
41. J. C. BARDHAN and N. C. GANGULY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1852.